

Foreign Direct Investment and Export Growth: A Meta-Analytic Perspective with Evidence from Developing and Developed Economies

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***Annotation.** Over the past several decades, the simultaneous surge in foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows and international trade, followed by the instability of these flows after the 2008–2009 global financial crisis, has sparked significant scholarly interest in their interrelationship. The expanding body of theoretical and empirical literature confirms this growing attention. Moreover, many countries have come to recognize the potential benefits of FDI, prompting governments to intensify competition for foreign capital by offering various incentives to attract investors. This trend has become particularly relevant in developing economies, where FDI serves as an important tool for promoting exports. However, empirical evidence on the impact of FDI on export performance remains mixed and inconclusive, making it difficult for host countries to formulate coherent and effective policy responses.*

***Keywords:** Export; Foreign Direct Investment (FDI); International Trade; Meta-Analysis; Globalization; Developing Economies; Policy Implications*

Introduction

The theoretical relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and exports is ambiguous, as FDI may either promote or hinder export performance depending on investors' motivations and the characteristics of both host and home countries. Consequently, the net effect of FDI on exports is ultimately an empirical matter. This ambiguity, combined with strong policy interest, has stimulated a growing body of empirical research on the topic.

Several studies have attempted to review the empirical literature on the FDI–export nexus. Forte (2004) offered one of the earliest systematic discussions, focusing primarily on theoretical models and including only a limited number of empirical studies. Tsaurai (2013) provided a broader chronological overview of selected empirical contributions; however, the selection criteria were not clearly defined, and no rigorous analytical or synthesis methodology was applied. Bayar (2018) examined determinants of exports more generally and identified FDI as an important factor, but his review relied on a very small set of empirical studies and lacked a systematic analytical framework.

Although these reviews address aspects of the same research question, they suffer from several important limitations. None adopts a clear host-country perspective, and all cover a relatively narrow range of empirical evidence. Moreover, most fail to engage with the theoretical foundations of the empirical studies and rely largely on descriptive approaches, without employing modern research synthesis techniques such as meta-regression analysis. As a result, their

findings are vulnerable to subjectivity and provide limited guidance for future research.

This study seeks to overcome these shortcomings by systematically synthesizing empirical evidence on the impact of FDI on host-country exports and by identifying sources of heterogeneity in reported results. We integrate the underlying theoretical frameworks and compile evidence from 117 empirical studies, making this meta-analysis the most comprehensive to date. Using meta-regression techniques, we quantitatively assess the macro-level effects of FDI on exports while minimizing bias and subjectivity.

In addition, unlike most previous reviews, our analysis incorporates micro-level evidence to illustrate how macro-level effects operate at the firm level within host countries. Finally, the study offers methodological recommendations to guide future empirical research on the FDI–export relationship.

Review of Theoretical Literature

This section reviews the theoretical foundations underlying the empirical studies analyzed later in the paper. Theoretical explanations of the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and host-country exports can be broadly classified into macro-level and micro-level approaches. Most macro-level models are rooted in either classical trade theory or New Trade Theory, while micro-level frameworks emphasize firm behavior and spillover mechanisms. A third strand integrates both perspectives within an eclectic framework (Dunning, 1977; Dunning & Lundan, 2008).

Macroeconomic trade theories generally assume either a complementary or substitutional relationship between FDI and trade. These models are typically formulated within general equilibrium frameworks and examine outcomes for both home and host countries, with host-country effects often analyzed through comparative statics (Mundell, 1957; Kojima, 1973). Complementarity implies a positive effect of FDI on host-country exports, whereas substitution suggests a weak or negative relationship.

Kojima's approach, grounded in Ricardian comparative advantage, predicts that FDI enhances host-country exports when investment targets sectors in which the home country lacks comparative advantage. Conversely, investment in sectors where the home country is already competitive leads to substitution and may reduce host-country exports (Kojima, 1973, 1975). Ozawa (1979) further refined this framework, which has since informed several empirical studies on export performance.

The emergence of New Trade Theory introduced models incorporating economies of scale, product differentiation, and imperfect competition (Krugman, 1980; Helpman & Krugman, 1987). Within this framework, three principal FDI models are distinguished: horizontal, vertical, and complex (integrated) FDI models. Horizontal FDI models emphasize market-seeking investment driven by trade costs and predict limited export effects, as subsidiary output is primarily sold in host-country markets, implying a substitutional relationship between FDI and trade (Markusen, 1984; Ethier & Markusen, 1996).

In contrast, vertical FDI models highlight production fragmentation across countries based on factor endowments, leading to complementarity between FDI and trade, particularly intra-firm trade (Helpman, 1984). These models are widely applied in empirical research, especially in developing-country contexts, where FDI often stimulates exports through technology transfer and integration into global value chains.

The knowledge-capital model integrates horizontal and vertical FDI within a unified framework, demonstrating that complementarity or substitution depends on factor endowments and trade costs (Markusen et al., 1996). Extensions of this model suggest that FDI is more likely to enhance exports in developing countries by facilitating efficient use of abundant production factors (Markusen, 1997).

Complex FDI models relax the strict horizontal–vertical dichotomy by allowing multinational subsidiaries to serve host, home, and third-country markets (Ekholm et al., 2007). Export-platform FDI models, in particular, show that declining trade costs increase the relevance of such strategies, improving export performance in small open economies (Yeaple, 2003). These models provide a direct theoretical basis for empirical studies on host-country export outcomes.

At the micro level, theories emphasize indirect channels such as spillovers, competition, skill upgrading, and learning-by-exporting. Firms initially self-select into export markets, but exporting itself can raise productivity and competitiveness over time (Clerides et al., 1998). Empirical evidence summarized by Martins and Yang (2009) confirms positive productivity effects of exporting, especially in developing economies.

Overall, theoretical models offer no unambiguous prediction regarding the export effects of FDI. The direction and magnitude of the relationship depend on country characteristics, investment motives, and market conditions. Consequently, the impact of FDI on host-country exports remains an empirical question, motivating the quantitative analysis undertaken in the subsequent section.

Research Methodology

This section outlines the data and methods used to estimate the meta-regression models. We first describe the procedures for identifying, collecting, and coding empirical estimates. We then summarize the main characteristics of the selected studies and finally present the meta-regression specifications and estimation strategy.

The meta-analytic database was constructed in accordance with the MAER-NET protocol (Stanley et al., 2013). A comprehensive literature search was conducted using Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Studies were identified by combining keywords related to foreign direct investment—such as *foreign direct investment*, *foreign ownership*, *multinational enterprise*, *spillovers*, and related variants—with the term *export*. Abbreviations and wildcard operators were applied to capture alternative expressions.

To ensure sample consistency, the analysis focused primarily on studies published in English, following established meta-analytic practice. The initial search yielded 5,298 records, which were screened in two stages: first through abstract review and subsequently through full-text examination of 447 articles.

Additional studies were identified using a snowballing approach based on backward and forward citation tracking. The search process was completed in July 2019.

To facilitate inference on the general macro-level effect of FDI on host-country exports, the final sample was restricted to relatively homogeneous econometric studies. Eligible studies were required to (i) include host-country exports as the dependent variable and (ii) incorporate FDI as an explanatory variable. Descriptive analyses and micro-level studies were excluded. No restrictions were imposed on publication year or country coverage. Both developed and developing countries were included, with their characteristics accounted for in the meta-regression framework. In addition to peer-reviewed journal articles, working papers and empirical monographs were considered.

The resulting dataset comprises 117 studies reporting 627 effect-size estimates, which form the basis of the empirical analysis.

Characteristics of the Selected Studies

Of the 117 studies, 77 focus on individual countries, while the remainder employ multi-country samples. Single-country studies cover a wide range of economies, including both developed and developing countries across Asia, Europe, Africa, and the Americas. Multi-country analyses typically concentrate on regional samples—most commonly Asia, Europe, Africa, and Latin America—while only a small number adopt a global perspective with coverage of up to 99 countries.

Developing economies dominate the samples in most multi-country studies. The studies in the dataset were published between 1975 and 2019, with data coverage spanning from 1960 to 2016. All sources included in the sample and their main findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The sample of studies

Study	Country	General Model	Industry Focus	General Impact
Riedel (1975)	Taiwan	Reduced export equation	Manufacturing sector	Insignificant
Lall and Mohammad (1983)	India	Reduced export equation	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Kojima (1985)	Japan and USA	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Nwanna (1986)	23 developing countries	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive

Smits (1988)	30 developing countries	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Erickson and Hayward (1991)	USA	Gravity	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Orr (1991)	USA	Reduced export equation	Manufacturing sector	Positive
O'Sullivan (1993)	Ireland	Structural	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Brouthers et al. (1996)	91 countries	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Leichenko and Erickson (1997)	USA	Reduced export equation	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Goldberg and Klein (1998)	Latin America and South-east Asia	Gravity	Whole economy	Positive
Kyrkilis, Pantelidis, and Papazoglou (1998)	USA	Gravity	Whole economy	Positive
Pain and Wakelin (1998)	Japan, USA, and EU	Reduced export equation	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Goldberg and Klein (1999)	Latin America	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Both
De Mello Jr and Fukasaku (2000)	Latin America and South-east Asia	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Sharma (2000)	India	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Insignificant
Hejazi and Safarian (2001)	USA	Gravity	Whole economy	Positive
Liu et al. (2001)	China	Gravity	Whole economy	Positive
Sun (2001)	China	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Zhang and Felmingham (2001)	China	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive

Zhang and Song (2001)	China	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Study	Country	General Model	Industry Focus	General Impact
Sahoo & Dash (2017)	India	Reduced export equation	Service sector	Positive
Sunde (2017)	South Africa	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Wattanakul (2017)	Laos	Structural	Whole economy	Positive
Wu & Wu (2017)	China	Structural	Whole economy	Positive
AhmadDraz & Yang (2018)	ASEAN-5	Structural	Whole economy	Insignificant
Çakërri (2018)	Albania	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Positive
Damoska Sekuloska (2018)	North Macedonia	Structural	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Jaćimović, Dragutinović, Mitrović, Bjelić, Tianping & Rajković (2018)	10 countries of Central Europe and West Balkans	Gravity	Whole economy	Positive
Maiga, Hu, Mekongcho & Coulibaly (2018)	ECOWAS	Structural	Whole economy	Insignificant
Popovici (2018)	EU	Reduced export equation	Manufacturing sector	Positive
Sargasyan & Grigoryan (2017)	Armenia	Reduced export equation	Whole economy	Negative

Description of Empirical Studies by Time and Focus

Based on the data presented in Table 1, macro-level studies on the impact of FDI on exports have been conducted since at least the 1970s. Early studies were carried out sporadically and primarily focused on developed countries.

From the late 1990s onwards, interest in this topic steadily increased, reaching a peak in 2017 when 17 articles were published. During this period, developing countries became the primary focus of empirical research.

Empirical findings indicate that more than three-quarters of the studies (approximately 75%) reported a positive impact of FDI on exports. The remaining 29 studies documented either negative or statistically insignificant results, suggesting a substitutive relationship between the variables.

However, substantial heterogeneity exists among the studies. These discrepancies provide the motivation for conducting our multivariate meta-regression analysis, whose main objective is to explain the sources of variation in the results.

Meta-Regression Model Specification and Evaluation Strategy

Meta-regression analysis allows for a systematic and more precise synthesis of empirical study results. This method enables the identification of factors that influence the outcomes of studies measuring the impact of FDI on exports. At the same time, the “overall export effect” obtained through meta-regression does not represent the true causal effect but rather reflects the effect estimated based on the available literature.

Measuring Effect Sizes

In the empirical literature, the impact of FDI on exports is measured using various methods, which creates a need for standardized effect measures to enable comparison of results.

One of the most commonly used measures is the **partial correlation coefficient**. For each observation, the following formula is applied (Stanley & Doucouliagos, 2012):

$$r_{ij} = \frac{t_{ij}}{\sqrt{t_{ij}^2 + df_{ij}}}$$

Here:

- t_{ij} — the t-statistic representing the effect of FDI on exports in the j-th specification of the i-th study
- df_{ij} — degrees of freedom

The standard errors (SE) of this effect size are calculated as follows

$$SE = \sqrt{\frac{1 - r_{ij}^2}{df_{ij}}}$$

Fixed-Effects and Random-Effects Meta-Regression Models

Methodologically, meta-regression models are considered in three main forms: simple OLS fixed-effects, WLS fixed-effects, and random-effects models. Their general formulation is as follows:

$$r_{ij} = \beta_0 + \mu_i + u_{ij}, \quad \mu_i \sim N(0, \tau^2), \quad u_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

- β_0 — intercept, i.e., the meta-analytic effect or average effect
- μ_i — individual effects, reflecting differences across studies
- u_{ij} — random disturbances, i.e., random error
- (3) OLS fixed-effects model

- (4) WLS fixed-effects model
- (5) Random-effects model

FAT-PET and PEESE models can also be applied in the form of a random-effects model:

$$r_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE + \mu_i + u_{ij}, \quad \mu_i \sim N(0, \tau^2), \quad u_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

$$r_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE^2 + \mu_i + u_{ij}, \quad \mu_i \sim N(0, \tau^2), \quad u_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

- $H_0: \beta_1 = 0$ — indicates the absence of publication bias
- If H_0 is rejected, it indicates statistically significant publication bias

Country Controls and Multiple Meta-Regression Model

Although publication bias is controlled using FAT-PET and PEESE tests, this alone is not sufficient to determine the true effect of FDI on exports. The main reason is that the observations come from different countries. Therefore, it is necessary to control for country-specific characteristics.

To achieve this, country dummy variables for each single-country study were included in the fixed-effects meta-regression model.

Empirical results

Our meta-analysis synthesizes empirical evidence from 117 studies and 627 observations on the effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) on host-country exports. The results from simple averages and meta-regression models—including fixed-effects (FEM), random-effects (REM), and weighted least squares fixed-effects (WLS-FEM) models—are reported in Table 2, focusing on the β_0 coefficient.

- Point estimates from simple averages, FEM, and REM are broadly similar. The WLS-FEM estimate is slightly higher, reflecting the greater precision of observations indicating a positive effect of FDI on exports.
- In all cases, coefficients are statistically significant at the 1% level. FEM estimates exhibit somewhat wider confidence intervals, suggesting lower precision. Overall, the evidence indicates a positive aggregate effect of FDI on exports, which, according to Doucouliagos (2011), can be interpreted as a moderate-intensity positive effect.

Table 2 | simple meta-analysis

Model	Coefficient	SE	Confidence Interval
Simple Average	0.263***	0.015	0.232 – 0.292
FEM	0.263***	0.024	0.215 – 0.309
WLS	0.307***	0.066	0.176 – 0.438
REM	0.259***	0.016	0.228 – 0.290

Table 3 | fat-pet and peese publication bias tests

Model	FAT-PET (FE)	PEESE (WLS)
Intercept (β_0)	0.226***	0.353***

SE	(0.039)	(0.111)
Publication Bias (β_1)	0.285	-1.114
SE	(0.220)	(1.064)
Observations	627	627
Studies	117	117
Hausman Test	17.813 (0.000)	16.264 (0.001)

Our meta-analysis finds no statistically significant differences in estimated effect sizes across studies due to functional form choice. In contrast, significant temporal heterogeneity is observed, indicating that the export effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) vary over time. This variation likely reflects increasing globalization, more complex global production networks, evolving industrialization strategies in developing economies, and changing policy attitudes toward foreign investment.

Controlling for total investment does not alter the main result: FDI continues to exert a positive and statistically significant effect on host-country exports, suggesting the presence of positive spillovers. Additional macro-level controls—such as exchange rates, foreign demand, export prices, infrastructure, business environment, and trade openness—generally do not materially affect the estimated relationship.

However, macro-level evidence alone cannot disentangle whether positive export effects arise from multinational enterprises (MNEs) themselves or from spillovers to domestic firms, nor can it identify the channels through which such spillovers operate. To address these limitations, we qualitatively synthesize the micro-level literature, as meta-analysis is unsuitable given the small number of studies and substantial heterogeneity in outcomes and methodologies.

Micro-level studies consistently show that foreign ownership is associated with higher export participation and intensity, though results vary across countries and ownership thresholds. Evidence from both developing and developed economies indicates that foreign-owned firms export more than domestic firms, while some non-linearities are observed, particularly in India and parts of Africa. Spillover studies further demonstrate that the presence of foreign firms can enhance domestic firms' export performance through horizontal, vertical, and regional channels, with effects often conditioned on absorptive capacity, geographic proximity, and trade openness.

Overall, the micro-level evidence largely corroborates macro-level and meta-analytic findings: FDI has predominantly positive direct and indirect effects on host-country exports. Mixed or insignificant results appear to be context-specific, reflecting differences in firm capabilities, institutional environments, and investor motivations.

Conclusion

This meta-analysis provides robust evidence that foreign direct investment (FDI) is an important driver of host-country export performance, with particularly strong effects in developing economies. The magnitude of these effects depends on country-specific conditions, including institutional quality, political stability, economic development, and the absorptive capacity of domestic firms. Micro-level

evidence further shows that export spillovers are spatially and sectorally concentrated, benefiting domestic firms that are geographically proximate to multinational enterprises and embedded in production and knowledge networks.

Despite its generally positive impact, the export effects of FDI are not uniform. Empirical estimates vary across methodological approaches, and potential adverse outcomes—such as crowding out of domestic investment or the transfer of obsolete technologies—cannot be ignored. These findings underscore the need for targeted, context-sensitive policy frameworks that align investment incentives with local capabilities and development objectives. Policies that promote knowledge diffusion, improve access to finance, and strengthen domestic firm competitiveness are essential to maximizing the export-enhancing effects of FDI while limiting potential risks.

Overall, FDI constitutes a dynamic but conditional source of export growth. Its effectiveness ultimately depends on supportive institutional environments, firm-level capacities, and evidence-based policy design aimed at fostering sustainable, export-led development.

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